

The Status of Indian minority communities: Progress, challenges and the Patna Ahead.

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Abstract:

As we know India is the largest Country in terms of population. In India there exist various religious Communities like Hindu, Muslim, Sikh, Christians, Buddhists, Jain, Parsi In this Country. Hindus nearly 80 percent of total population with an estimated 172.2 million. Whereas Muslim population 27.8 million, Christian 20.8 million etc. Here we can see the population of some group are small in Society that is different from the rest; and these group are called Minority. The Controversial term "minority" or minorities is used in the Constitution in some articles like Article 29, the Article 30, Article 350(A) and the 350(B) but a concrete definition is not given in the Constitution. The Union government under the National Commission on Minorities Act 1992 has recognized 5 minority communities that is Muslim, Christians, Sikhs, Buddhists Parsis and Jains (Jains were added later in 2014). The social economic condition of minorities is very low. The programme of Ms DP for minority that improving the socio-economic parameters of basic amenities for improving the quality of life of the people and reducing imbalances in the minority concentration areas.

Keywords: Amenities, progress, Controversial, population, minorities, social, amenities, efforts, improving, ending, imbalances, programme.

Introduction:

India, known for its rich diversity is home to numerous minority communities contributing to the country's cultural fabric, the term "minorities communities" refers to groups that constitute a smaller proportion of the total population and are distinct from the majority community in terms of religion, language, ethnicity, or other characteristics. This article aims to shed light on the current status of Indian minority communities, their progress, challenges they face and the efforts made by the government and society to address their concerns.

Demographics of Minority Communities:

Indian minority communities consist of various religious, linguistic, and ethnic groups including Muslims, Christians, Sikhs, Buddhists, Jains, Parsis, and others. As per the 2011 census, Minorities constituted about 19.3% of India's population, with Muslim being the largest minority group, followed by Christians, Sikhs, Buddhists, Jains, and others.

Progress and Achievement:

Over the years minority communities in India have made significant contributions to the nation's growth and development. Many individuals from minority backgrounds have excelled in various fields, including politics, sports, Arts, Science, and business showcasing their talent and potential. Government policies and initiatives have also played a role in empowering and uplifting these communities through scholarships, reservation, and socio-economic programs.

Educational Empowerment:

Education is seen as a key factor in the progress of minority communities. Various

educational schemes and scholarships have been implemented to ensure better access to education for children belonging to minority backgrounds. These efforts have resulted in increased literacy rates and improved educational outcomes.

Socio-Economic Challenges:

Despite notable progress, minority communities continue to face socio-economic challenges, including poverty, unemployment, and limited access to basic amenities in some areas. The lack of equal opportunities has hindered the socio-economic development of many individuals within these communities.

Religious Harmony and communal Tension:

India's secular fabric is woven with religious beliefs and practices. However, communal tensions and instances of religious discrimination have been a concern, leading to occasional conflicts. Encouraging inter-faith dialogue, promoting religious harmony, and ensuring the protection of minority rights are crucial for fostering an inclusive society.

Empowerment Initiatives:

The Government of India has introduced various schemes and policies aimed at empowering minority communities such as the MDP programme, which will be prepared on the basis of the development deficits brought out by a baseline survey, would be to improve the socio-economic parameters of the district as a whole so as to bring them at par with the national average if not higher. Also a new programme launched by the prime minister's new 15 point programme National Minorities Development and Finance Corporation (NMDFC), and various scholarship programs.

The role of civil society and NGOs:

Civil society organization and non-government organizations (NGOs) play a crucial role on advocating for minority rights and providing assistance in areas like education, health care and skill development. The central government launch the multi-sectoral Development program (MSDP) for minority can central areas.

Substantial minority population in the context of the prime ministers New 15 point programme has been used for identification of districts which are relatively backward in which at least 25% of the total population belongs to minority communities has been used for identification of MCD, MCBs and MCTs. Where a minority community is in majority in the six states/ UTs 15% of minority population other than that of minority community in majority in that state/UTs, has been used here also used a parameters for finding minority concentration districts that's called the backwardness parameter following are the backwardness parameters:-

- Religious specific socio- economic indicators at the District level.
- Literacy rate.
- Female literacy rate.
- Work participation rate ; and female work participation rate.
- Basic amenities indicators at the District level.
- Percentage of house holds with pucca walls
- Percentage of house holds with safe drinking water, and
- Percentage of house holds with electricity.

One the base of above parameter how many minority concentration area were identified? The answer is 90 minority concentration Blocks and 66 minority concentration towns have been identified on the basis of both population data and backwardness parameters of census 2001. The multi sectoral Development programme was implemented in these 90 MCDs during 11th plan and 2012-13 period. Whereas 710 MCBs and 66 MCTs where the area unit for implementation of MSDP during 2013-14 and 2017-18.

In 1987 a list of 41 minority concentration districts was prepared , based on the data of census 1971. A single criterion of minority population of 20 percent or more in a district was applied for identification of 41 districts. Minority concentration area have been identified by government which are relatively backward and falling behind the national average in terms of socio-economic and basic amenities indicators. These are as have a substantial minority population and are backward, with unacceptably low levels of socio- economic or basic amenities, indicators, requiring focused attention and specific programme intervention.

Challenges:

Violence against minorities in India are challenging in the path of their development. Noe a days this a serious subject, violence against minorities in india. Communal violence in India has a complex history and dynamic that spans decades. It is primarily rooted in religious and ethnic tensions between different communities. Instances of communal violence have been recorded throughout India's history , but particularly during critical periods like that , partition of India 1947, January - March 1964, West Bengal/ Bihar/ Orissa/riots, August 1967, Ranchi , Bihar, riots, September 1969 Ahamdabad, Gujrat Riots, April 1979, Jamshedpur, Bihar Riots, August- November 1980, Muradabad , UP, February 1983, Nellie , Assam violence, etc.

There are so many violence which we can't describe here due to there horrible seen and mainly this is not the main topic of this articles but one violence which are done in in manipur currently 3rd May 2023 between kukee and maitai tribe. This violence is also done in minority communities main cause of this violence not yet found but this violence is very shame full and pain full for all Indians. Communal violence in India has a complex history and dynamic that spans decades. It is primarily rooted in religious and ethnic tensions between different communities. Instances of communal violence have been recorded throughout India's history, but particularly during critical periods like the partition of India in 1947 and various communal riots in different states. The main factors contributing to communal violence include socio-political factors, economic disparities and political manipulation, communal incidents are often triggered by events that incite religious or communal sentiments, leading to clashes between different groups. Some scholars and researchers review on the status of minorities communities in India and other country.

Arend Lijphart (1996): India has been the one major deviant case for consociational (power sharing) theory, and its sheer size makes the exception especially damaging. A deeply divided society with, supposed by, a mainly majoritarian type of democracy , india nevertheless has been able to maintain its democratic system . Careful examination reveals, however , that Indian democracy has displayed all four crucial elements of power sharing theory. In fact, it was a perfectly and thoroughly consociational system during its first two decades. From the late 1960s on although India has remained basically consociational , some of its power sharing elements have weakened under the pressure of great mass mobilization. Concomitantly, in accordance with consociational theory, intergroup hostility and violence have increased. There for India is not a deviant case for consociational theory but, instead, an impressive conforming case.

Mary o odate, David C Talavera, Soumia cheref, Judy H Hong, Rheoda L Walker (2016):

There has been an increase in literature that addresses risks associated with suicide vulnerability and death for Americans Indian/Alaska Native Asian American, Black American, and Hispanic American adults the dearth of literature is also addressed by the proposition of emergent needs in the study of ethnic minority suicide.

A review of empirical studies and conceptual reports published in the last decade revealed common trends associated with suicide across ethnic groups, including socio demographic variables, Psychiatric risks, cultural factors, and factors related to interpersonal relations. Ethnic minority groups also shared notable protective factors such as religious and spiritual beliefs and familial ties. Suggested direction for future research include the examination of individual subgroups within ethnic communities as well as the exploration of understudied correlates that show promising evidence as influential to suicidal behavior.

Muhammad Roy Purwanto(2017): This research attempts to look at the problem mapping of Muslim minorities in Allahabad India and Bali Indonesia. Allahabad is a holy city of Hindu religion. While Bali is an island and province of Indonesia, with most of Indonesians Hindu live problem of Muslim minorities in the both was exciting to be researched and mapped further. How is the relationship between the majority and minority, relationship between minorities and the state. The problem of economic inequality, Political inequality, and social inequality tolerance and intolerance attitude of community. Hear after studying about the minorities status we can say our country is far behind the humanities, and development.

Efforts to curb communal violence have been made through legal measures, police intervention and community initiatives. However underlying issues and deep rooted prejudices still pose challenges in achieving lasting peace and harmony. It is essential to approach the topic with sensitivity and recognize that communal violence is a complex and multi-dimensional issue that requires comprehensive understanding and solution.

Conclusion:

India's minority communities have contributed significantly to the nation's diverse cultural tapestry and continue to strive for progress and prosperity. While there have been positive steps taken to uplift these communities, there remain challenges that need continued attention and collective effort from the government, civil society and society as a whole promoting inclusivity religious harmony and equal opportunities for all is

essential to build a stronger and more united India, where every citizen can thrive regardless of their background.

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